

INTERACTION OF CHARCOAL WITH CHLORINE WATER

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The interaction of charcoal with chlorine water has been investigated. The reaction appears to involve the conversion of chlorine into hydrochloric acid and surface oxidation of charcoal. The reaction is fairly vigorous to begin with, slows down soon after and ultimately stops. The capacity of charcoal to bring about the reaction appears to depend on its capacity to chemisorb oxygen.

The interaction of charcoal with chlorine water has not been properly investigated although it is reported (Behram and Gustafson, *Ind. Eng. Chem.* 1935, 27, 426) that activated charcoal can be employed for the removal of chlorine and iodine from water. In view of the fact that activated carbon has general adsorption tendency towards oxidising agents (Kruyt, "Colloids", 1930, John Wiley & Sons, N.Y.), it would be of interest to know whether the halogens are adsorbed because of their behaviour as oxidising agents. The present paper describes the results obtained on treating different samples of charcoal with chlorine water which appear to throw some light on the mechanism of the reaction involved.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two varieties of charcoal, prepared by the carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar (by means of pure sulphuric acid followed by exhaustive washings with hot distilled water) and coconut shells (by heating small pieces at about 350° in a limited supply of air), were used in the various experiments. Sugar charcoal was almost free of ash, while the coconut-shell charcoal was extracted with hydrofluoric acid to lower its ash content to about 0.25%.

Each sample was divided into three portions: one was labelled as "original sample" and was used as such; the second was "activated" in vacuum at 700°, and the third at 1200° in order to remove all types of oxygen and adsorption complexes. A part of the sample, degassed at 1200° (10 g. at a time), was reactivated in a stream of oxygen (2 litres/hr.) at 400° for 8 hours. This treatment has been shown (Puri, Nath and Sharma, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1956, 44, 1309; Weller and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 4155) to result in the 'fixation' of a large amount of oxygen.

A 0.075*N* solution of chlorine in water could be easily prepared at the prevailing temperature and was used in the various experiments.

Procedure.—Charcoal (2 g. sample) was mixed with chlorine water (400 c.c.) and the suspension shaken mechanically for different intervals of time in preliminary experiments, and for about 5 hours in subsequent experiments in closed bottles (wrapped in thick black papers) of 600 c.c. capacity, after which an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid was examined for free chlorine and hydrochloric acid by the usual analytical methods.

The various samples of charcoal, before as well as after treatment with chlorine water, were subjected to evacuation in a resistance tube furnace at 1200°, and the gases evolved were analysed in the following sequence: Water was removed in calcium chloride tubes and carbon dioxide in a series of Erlenmeyer flasks containing a known amount of barium hydroxide solution. Carbon monoxide and hydrogen in the rest of the gaseous mixture were estimated in Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus in the usual way.

TABLE I

Conversion of chlorine water into hydrochloric acid after shaking for diff. intervals of time.

Amount of chlorine initially taken = .30 m.e. (400 c.c. of 0.075N soln.).

Time of shaking.	Amount of hydrochloric acid formed							
	Without charcoal.			With charcoal				
	Cl ₂ left unchanged.	HCl formed.	Total of 2 and 3.	Cl ₂ left unchanged.	HCl in soln.	HCl re-covered from charcoal.	Total HCl formed.	Total of Cl ₂ & HCl.
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
15 min.	29.05 m.e.	0.40 m.e.	29.45 m.e.	14.98 m.e.	13.55 m.e.	0.82 m.e.	14.37 m.e.	29.35 m.e.
30	29.04	0.46	29.50	11.73	16.70	0.86	17.56	29.29
60	29.11	0.49	29.60	9.53	18.85	0.92	19.77	29.30
120	29.01	0.54	29.55	8.18	20.20	1.02	21.22	29.40
240	28.95	0.60	29.55	6.94	21.45	0.96	22.41	29.35
360	28.86	0.64	29.50	6.83	21.50	1.00	22.50	29.33
480	29.02	0.65	29.67	6.86	21.45	1.04	22.49	29.35

DISCUSSION

It is seen (Table I) that while in the presence of charcoal the conversion of chlorine into hydrochloric acid takes place appreciably, in its absence it takes place only to the extent of about 2%. The hydrochloric acid formed was found to be mostly in solution; only a small amount was adsorbed by charcoal which too could be recovered on washing with hot distilled water as shown in the table. The reaction seems to be fairly rapid to begin with which shows incidentally that charcoal is highly efficient for the removal of chlorine gas from water. However, the reaction appears to come to a stand-still after about 4 hours. This might be attributed to the very low concentration of chlorine left in the solution at this stage. In order to verify this, the supernatant liquid, after the attainment of equilibrium, was replaced by a fresh solution (400 c.c.) of the gas. The analysis of this solution, after 5 hours shaking with charcoal, showed that only 4.8 m.e. of the gas had changed into hydrochloric acid. Subsequent renewal of chlorine water, however, did not produce any more hydrochloric acid, even when the shaking was extended for a further period of 6 hours.

It is evident therefore that the reaction ultimately tends to come to a 'stop'. Thus, charcoal does not act as a catalyst in the ordinary sense of the term. Rather, it is more likely that charcoal itself takes part in the reaction as a result of which it is changed into a form in which it is incapable of 'reacting' further.

As the entire amount of chlorine added to charcoal is accounted for either as chlorine gas left unchanged or as hydrochloric acid produced (Table I), it is evident that none of it is fixed by charcoal as such.

TABLE II

Conversion of chlorine into hydrochloric acid in the presence of variously treated samples of charcoal.

Nature of charcoal.	Amount of hydrochloric acid (in m.e.) formed in case of					
	Sugar charcoal.			Coconut-shell charcoal.		
	In soln.	Recovered from charcoal.	Total formed.	In soln.	Recovered from charcoal.	Total formed.
Original	25.71	1.50	27.21	19.18	0.86	20.04
Evac. at 750°	21.08	1.88	22.96	16.98	0.92	17.90
Evac. at 1200°	12.67	2.29	14.87	10.82	0.96	11.78
Evac. at 1200° & treated with O ₂ at 400°	27.75	1.58	29.43	22.02	0.84	22.86

The results obtained with the various samples of sugar and coconut-shell charcoals (2 g.) after treating twice with 400 c.c. of 0.075*N* chlorine water in the manner, explained above, are recorded in Table II. The capacity of the "original" samples to convert chlorine into hydrochloric acid is seen to decrease progressively on degassing at 700° and 1200°. However, when the completely degassed samples are treated with oxygen, the initial capacity (for the reaction) is more than restored. It is also seen that the sugar charcoal has a greater capacity for the reaction than the coconut-shell charcoal. This may perhaps be due to greater surface area of the former (Puri and Sharma, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, 15B, 178).

The conversion of chlorine water into hydrochloric acid evidently involves the well-known reaction,

The function of the charcoal presumably is to take up this oxygen in some form and its capacity to take up the oxygen probably determines its capacity to bring about the reaction. Now this oxygen may either give rise to low temperature combustion of charcoal or may be chemisorbed. The former possibility was tested by analysing the gas above the reaction mixture, in each bottle, in Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus, and the latter by evacuating the charcoal at 1200° (after drying in air-oven at 150°) and carefully analysing the gases evolved. However, little or no carbon dioxide or carbon monoxide was found in the space above the reaction mixture, showing complete absence of low-temperature combustion. The results of the evacuation experiments (Table III) show that more carbon dioxide is evolved from the samples after treatment with chlorine water than before, and consequently there is an increase in the total oxygen (calculated from CO₂, CO and H₂O evolved) as well. This shows clearly that most of the oxygen

resulting from the conversion of chlorine into hydrochloric acid, becomes chemisorbed by charcoal and that it is almost entirely disposed of as carbon dioxide and is evolved as such on high temperature evacuation. It is interesting to note that the sample evacuated at 1200°, which is almost free of oxygen, chemisorbs an appreciable amount of oxygen on treatment with chlorine water.

TABLE III

Amounts of gases evolved on evacuating at 1200° from different samples of sugar charcoal before and after treatment with chlorine water.

Nature of sample.	Amounts of gases evolved (mg./g.).				Total oxygen evolved as CO ₂ , CO & H ₂ O (mg./g.)	Increase in on treatment with Cl ₂ (mg./g.)	O ₂ content in terms of m.e./g.	Amount of HCl produced as per eq. (1) (m.e./g.)
	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ O.	H ₂ .				
Original:								
Before treatment	134.2	155.0	125.0	14.96	297.18	93.94	11.75	13.50
After treatment	246.6	149.9	141.9	13.78	391.12			
Evacuated at 750°:								
Before treatment	4.4	112.4	64.5	12.60	124.74	84.76	10.59	11.48
After treatment	101.2	115.3	78.7	11.54	209.50			
Evacuated at 1200°:								
Before treatment	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	53.02	6.63	7.43
After treatment	62.4	Nil	8.6	Nil	53.02			
Evacuated at 1200° & treated with O ₂ at 400°:								
Before treatment	83.1	83.6	36.0	Nil	143.07	107.52	13.44	14.71
After treatment	230.2	89.1	36.3	Nil	250.59			

The increase in the oxygen content of each sample, expressed in terms of mg./g. is given in column 7 and in terms of m.e./g. in column 8 (Table III). It is interesting to note that the m.e. of oxygen chemisorbed per g. charcoal agrees fairly well with the m.e. of HCl produced (column 9) during the reaction, as required by the stoichiometric equation given above. Thus, the entire amount of the oxygen evolved during the reaction is accounted for. Evidently, this oxygen is chemisorbed by charcoal and enriches its oxygen complexes so long as the charcoal is in a position to take up oxygen.

The presence of oxygen complexes in charcoal is known to affect appreciably its surface behaviour and surface properties such as acid-base adsorption, moisture retention, ammonia adsorption and heat of wetting (Weller and Young, *loc. cit.*; Puri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*; Bruns, Maximova and Pos, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 63, 286; Pierce *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4551; Anderson and Emmett, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 756; Kraus, *ibid.*, 1955, 59, 343). The treatment of charcoal with chlorine water thus places at our disposal a convenient method for preparing charcoals with such characteristics. This is also an interesting case of low-temperature surface oxidation of charcoal.